

Synthesis, antitumor and antioxidant activity studies of cyanopyridones

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Abstract : Cyanopyridone derivatives are generated by both microwave assisted and conventional methods. The condensation of chalcones with ethylcyanoacetate in the presence of ammonium acetate in ethanol leads to cyanopyridones. In microwave synthesis, the reactions are considerably faster and the yields are significantly higher compared to conventionally heated reactions. All compounds were tested for antitumor and antioxidant activities and structures were confirmed by spectral analysis.

Keywords : Cyanopyridones, antitumor and antioxidant activity.

Introduction

Pyridones play a vital part in numerous biological processes and have significant importance having therapeutic activities which includes antiviral¹, 5 α -reductase inhibitors¹, anti-tumor¹, analgesic², anti-inflammatory² and antipyretic² properties. Also known as specific non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor of human immunodeficiency virus-1 (HIV-1)³.

Quite a lot of synthetic approaches to 2-pyridones have been reported in the literature. 3-Cyano-2-pyridones synthesis has been described by the use of cyanoacetamide in condensations with enones. 3-Cyano-2-pyridones possess various biological and pharmacological activity, particularly antimicrobial⁴, antidepressant⁴, cardiotoxic⁴ and anticancer activity⁴. There is much importance in the anticancer activity of these compounds due to different types of biological targets they might interfere with for this effect to occur e.g. PDE3, PIM1 Kinase and Survivin protein⁴.

This paper explains a simplistic synthesis of cyanopyridone by condensation of chalcones with ethyl cyanoacetate by use of microwave irradiation. These compounds were tested for anti-tumor and antioxidant activity.

Experimental

Melting points were found by capillary method and were uncorrected. Shimadzu Perkin-Elmer 8201 Pc IR

spectrometer used in recording IR spectra (KBr pellets) and frequencies are expressed in cm^{-1} . Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer recorded PMR spectra. All spectra were obtained in CDCl_3 and DMSO. Chemical shift values are reported as values in ppm relative to TMS ($\delta = 0$) as internal standard. JEOL SX-102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer recorded FAB mass spectra using Argon/Xenon (6 Kv, 10 Ma) as the FAB gas. The elemental analyses have been obtained using Vairo Elementar Model, CHN analyser and the results were found to be within $\pm 0.4\%$. Cata-R, Catalyst Systems 140-700 W microwave reactor was used for microwave synthesis.

General methods of synthesis of substituted chalcones (JC1-JC8) :

Synthesis of 3-(anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(aryl substituted) prop-2-en-1-one :

9-Anthraldehyde (0.01 mol) and substituted acetophenones (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) were stirred together for 24 h. 20% NaOH (4 ml) were used as catalyst. After the completion of the reaction, it was poured into crushed ice and acidified with HCl. The solvent ethanol was used for recrystallisation⁵.

3-(Anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(4-bromophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC1) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 80-82 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3040 (CH str.), 1694 (α, β -unsaturated keto group), 1509 (C=C str.), 668 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ

ppm : 7.26–7.28 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, H-2), 7.4–7.43 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz, H-3), 7.27–7.29 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44–7.45 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.48–7.56 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.30–7.37 (6H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 128.9 (C-Br), 125.3, 128.3, 125.4, 125.3, 125.6, 121.6, 128.3, 125.2, 125.9, 123.5 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 133.1, 136.0 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺) 387, (M⁺ 2) 389. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 71.33; H, 3.90. Found : C, 71.36; H, 3.87.

3-(Anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(4-fluorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC2) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 83–85 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3041, 3007 (CH str.), 1696 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1504 (C=C str.), 1338 (C-F); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.41–7.43 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz, H-2), 7.53–7.54 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.22–7.25 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.42–7.45 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.92–8.16 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.25–8.29 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.29 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 168.7 (C-F), 125.4, 128.5, 126.4, 123.3, 121.4, 127.2, 124.2, 126.6, 124.2 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 133.4, 136.8 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺ 1) 327. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 84.64; H, 4.63. Found : C, 84.60; H, 4.65.

3-(Anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC3) :

Cream crystals, m.p. 103–105 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3125 (CH str.), 1675 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1510 (C=C str.), 1513 (C-NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.04–7.05 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, H-2), 7.13–7.14 (1H, d, *J* 15.7 Hz, H-3), 7.24–7.25 (2H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.26–7.28 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.91–8.15 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.35–8.40 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.3 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 153.7 (C-NO₂), 125.1, 128.2, 125.5, 126.2, 126.6, 125.5, 128.2, 127.6, 125.7, 122.2 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-

5'', C-6''), 133.6, 135.6 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺ 1) 353. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 78.17; H, 4.28. Found : C, 78.19; H, 4.26.

3-(Anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC4) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 87–89 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3048, (CH str.), 1675 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1510 (C=C str.), 748 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.43–7.44 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, H-2), 7.55–7.57 (1H, d, *J* 15.7 Hz, H-3), 7.20 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 7.39 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.86–7.89 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.54–8.58 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.2 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 168.7 (C-F), 125.3, 126.5, 126.4, 122.1, 121.5, 126.1, 123.1, 125.2, 124.2 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 133.5, 137.8 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺) 342. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 80.58; H, 4.41. Found : C, 80.59; H, 4.43.

3-(Anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(4-aminophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC5) :

Light yellow crystals, m.p. 96–98 °C ; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3012 (CH str.), 1693 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1514 (C=C str.), 3512, 3215 (NH₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.45–7.47 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, H-2), 7.48–7.49 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz, H-3), 7.12–7.14 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 7.41–7.44 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.88–7.92 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.13–8.17 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.1 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 154.2 (C-NH₂), 122.4, 128.3, 126.2, 125.3, 126.4, 127.5, 124.2, 126.2, 126.5, 124.5 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 135.4, 135.4 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺) 228. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 85.42; H, 5.30. Found : C, 85.43; H, 5.46.

3-(Anthracenyl-9-yl)-1-(4-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC6) :

Brown crystals, m.p. 88–89 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3053 (CH str.), 1693 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1502 (C=C str.), 3613 (OH); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.51–7.52 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, H-2), 7.54–7.56 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz, H-3), 7.22–7.25 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.42–

7.45 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.89–7.93 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.21–8.24 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.27–8.29 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 164.7 (C-OH), 125.4, 128.5, 125.6, 123.7, 121.4, 127.8, 124.2, 123.6, 124.2 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 132.4, 137.3 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺) 324. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 85.16; H, 4.97. Found : C, 85.19; H, 4.96.

3-(Anthracen-9-yl)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC7) :

Cream crystals, m.p. 93–95 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3041 (CH str.), 1692 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1504 (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.46–7.48 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz, H-2), 7.43–7.45 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz, H-3), 7.24–7.26 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.49–7.51 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.97–8.11 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.27–8.32 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.3 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 166.4, 55.6 (C-OCH₃), 126.4, 127.5, 126.6, 123.5, 122.4, 127.2, 125.2, 127.3, 124.4, 124.7 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 133.4, 137.5 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺) 338. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 85.18; H, 5.36. Found : C, 85.19; H, 5.35.

3-(Anthracen-9-yl)-1-(3-bromophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (JC8) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 111–112 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3052 (CH str.), 1697 (α,β-unsaturated keto group), 1512 (C=C str.), 652 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 7.52–7.53 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz, H-2), 7.56–7.57 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, H-3), 7.21–7.23 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.42–7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.91–7.96 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.24–8.28 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.21 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 187.7 (C=O, C-1), 121.2, 145.1 (CH=CH, C-2, C-3), 128.7 (C-Br), 125.7, 127.5, 127.4, 126.3, 121.4, 127.2, 123.2, 123.6, 122.2 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 133.7, 136.4 (2C aromatic, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) (M⁺) 354. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 71.33; H, 3.90. Found : C,

71.31; H, 3.88.

General methods of synthesis of substituted cyanopyridones (CP1-CP8) :

Synthesis of 4-(anthracen-9-yl)-6-(aryl substituted)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile :

A mixture of chalcone (0.01 mol), ethyl cyanoacetate (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.08 mol) in DMF (10 ml) was subjected to microwave irradiation for 6–8 min. With constant stirring, the reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The product thus obtained was recrystallized from ethanol. Ethyl acetate : chloroform (8 : 2) is the solvent system for TLC. The same was carried under conventional heating by refluxing the reaction mixture for 12–14 h^{6,7}.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP1) :

Reddish brown crystals, m.p. 121–123 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3080 (aromatic CH str.), 1523 (C=C), 1654 (C=N), 1729 (C=O), 749 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.85 (2H, s, -CH₂), 6.90–6.93 (2H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.21–7.22 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.89–7.94 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.40–8.44 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.90–8.92 (2H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 164.2 (C, C-2), 126.2 (C, C-3), 136.7 (C, C-4''), 38.9 (C, C-5), 128.3, 127.3, 125.4, 125.8, 125.6, 128.3, 123.4, 126.3, 125.7, 126.6 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 172.2, 164.4, 132.3, 131.4 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) : (M⁺) 406, (M⁺ + 2) 408. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 76.75; H, 3.72. Found : C, 76.73; H, 3.71.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-nitrophenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP2) :

Brown crystals, m.p. 142–144 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3030 (aromatic CH str.), 1515 (C=C), 1628 (C=N), 1700 (C=O), 1423 (C-NO₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.81 (2H, s, -CH₂), 7.25–7.27 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46–7.49 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.53–7.58 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.02–8.04 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 8.3 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 164.4 (C, C-2), 125.2 (C, C-3), 150.4 (C, C-4''), 38.5 (C, C-5), 128.2, 125.2, 128.8, 126.6, 128.3, 122.4, 125.3, 124.2, 126.3 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-

6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 173.2, 164.6, 133.5, 132.4 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (m/z): (M^+) 417. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 74.81; H, 3.62. Found : C, 74.83; H, 3.64.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP3) :

Brown crystals, m.p. 162–164 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3048 (aromatic CH str.), 1609 (C=C), 1649 (C=N), 1719 (C=O), 1231 (C-F); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.54 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 6.86–6.88 (2H, d, J 9.7 Hz, Ar-H), 6.94 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83–7.88 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.42–8.46 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.71–8.72 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ ppm : 163.2 (C, C-2), 121.5 (C, C-3), 165.5 (C, C-4''), 38.3 (C, C-5), 126.2, 125.4, 124.4, 125.2, 124.7, 128.2, 123.3, 125.2, 126.4, 125.2 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 171.3, 164.4, 132.5, 132.5 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (m/z): (M^+ 2) 390. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 79.99; H, 3.87. Found : C, 79.97; H, 3.84.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-bromophenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP4) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 126–128 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3123 (aromatic CH str.), 1598 (C=C), 1692 (C=N), 1702 (C=O), 621 (C-Br); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.99 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 7.17–19 (1H, d, H_a), 7.25–7.27 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.39–7.43 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.44 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.89–7.92 (2H, d, J 9.4 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 164.1 (C, C-2), 126.6 (C, C-3), 124.4 (C, C-4''), 38.1 (C, C-5), 127.3, 126.1, 126.4, 125.2, 127.7, 125.2, 123.4, 126.3, 125.5, 125.4, 126.8 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 171.4, 167.2, 131.5, 132.5 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (m/z): (M^+) 450, (M^+ 2) 452. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 69.19; H, 3.35. Found : C, 69.22; H, 3.38.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-aminophenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP5) :

Yellowish brown crystals, m.p. 204–206 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3112 (aromatic CH str.), 1538 (C=C), 1665 (C=N), 1715 (C=O), 732 (C-Cl); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.85 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 6.96–6.98 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.24–7.26 (1H, d, J 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.91–7.95 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.67–8.69 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.88–8.89

(2H, d, J 9.2 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ ppm : 164.2 (C, C-2), 126.2 (C, C-3), 136.7 (C, C-4''), 38.9 (C, C-5), 127.3, 127.4, 126.4, 125.4, 122.4, 123.5, 122.4, 123.3, 124.7, 126.3 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 171.2, 163.4, 133.1, 131.3 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (m/z): (M^+) 387. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 80.60; H, 4.42. Found : C, 80.59; H, 4.40.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP6) :

Cream crystals, m.p. 131–133 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3083 (aromatic CH str.), 1542 (C=C), 1657 (C=N), 1725 (C=O), 3621 (OH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.81 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 7.12–7.14 (2H, d, J 9.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.24–7.25 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.35–7.39 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.44 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.90–7.92 (2H, d, J 9.3 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ ppm : 164.2 (C, C-2), 126.2 (C, C-3), 136.7 (C, C-4''), 38.9 (C, C-5), 124.1, 127.4, 125.2, 126.8, 126.3, 123.1, 124.3, 125.2, 126.4 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 171.2, 163.4, 132.2, 131.5 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (m/z): (M^+) 388. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 80.40; H, 4.15. Found : C, 80.41; H, 4.16.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP7) :

Reddish brown crystals, m.p. 146–148 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3063 (aromatic CH str.), 1532 (C=C), 1668 (C=N), 1737 (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.76 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2$), 6.78 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz, Ar-H), 6.97–6.99 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.21–7.25 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.42–7.44 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.89–7.91 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz), 8.8 (1H, s, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ ppm : 164.2 (C, C-2), 126.2 (C, C-3), 136.7 (C, C-4''), 38.9 (C, C-5), 123.3, 124.3, 126.4, 126.7, 122.8, 124.6, 127.3, 123.1, 126.2, 121.7, 125.6 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 172.1, 163.4, 131.3, 131.4 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (m/z): (M^+) 402. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 80.58; H, 4.51. Found : C, 80.59; H, 4.50.

4-(Anthracen-9-yl)-6-(3-bromophenyl)-2-oxo-2,5-dihydropyridine-3-carbonitrile (CP8) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 131–133 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} :

3065 (aromatic CH str.), 1536 (C=C), 1664 (C=N), 1743 (C=O), 635 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ ppm : 2.6 (2H, s, -CH₂), 6.90–6.93 (2H, d, *J* 9.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.82–7.87 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.04–8.08 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.19–8.12 (2H, d, *J* 9.4 Hz, Ar-H), 8.5 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ ppm : 164.2 (C, C-2), 126.2 (C, C-3), 136.7 (C, C-4''), 38.9 (C, C-5), 122.3, 128.3, 125.2, 125.2, 121.6, 124.3, 122.4, 125.3, 125.7, 126.6 (13 CH aromatic, C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5', C-6', C-7', C-8', C-10', C-2'', C-3'', C-5'', C-6''), 173.2, 163.4, 131.3, 131.4 (4C aromatic, C-4, C-5, C-9, C-1''); Mass (*m/z*) : (M⁺) 406, (M⁺ + 2) 408. Anal. Calcd. for : C, 76.75; H, 3.72. Found : C, 76.73; H, 3.71.

Evaluation of anticancer activity :

The test compounds are studied for short term *in vitro* cytotoxicity against Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma (EAC) cells. Trypan Blue Exclusion was the method used for viability checking of the tumor cells aspirated from peritoneal cavity of tumor bearing mice. To the tubes containing various concentrations of the test compounds, the cell suspension was added and volume was made up to 1 ml using phosphate buffered saline (PBS). Control tubes were of only cell suspension. After 3 h incubation period at 37 °C the percent of dead cells were calculated⁸.

Evaluation of antioxidant activity :

DPPH radical scavenging activity :

The stable radical DPPH was used as the reagent in this spectrophotometric assay⁹. 3 ml of 0.1 mM solution of DPPH and 1 ml of the compounds bearing different concentrations (10–200 µg/ml) was mixed and was kept in dark for 30 min. It was incubated for 30 min at room temperature, and the absorbance was read against blank at 517 nm.

Nitric oxide free radical scavenging method :

Nitric oxide radicals (NO) were generated from sodium nitroprusside. To the different concentrations (10–200 µg/ml) of the test compounds, 1 ml of sodium nitroprusside (10 mM) and 1.5 ml of phosphate buffer saline (0.2 M, pH 7.4) were added. These mixtures were incubated for 150 min at 25 °C and 1 ml of the reaction mixture was treated with 1 ml of Griess reagent. The absorbance was taken at 546 nm. The results were expressed for both antioxidant methods as percentage of inhibition, which was calculated according to the following equation¹⁰,

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Control absorbance} - \text{Test absorbance}}{\text{Control absorbance}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

Microwave irradiation method afforded the desired cyanopyridones in good yields (75–86%) from an equimolar mixture of chalcones and ethylcyanoacetate in DMF with catalytic amounts of ammonium acetate. Under conventional heating methods, reactions were initially tried using DMF as solvent, resulted in longer reaction times (12–14 h) with low yields (60–70%) (Fig. 1).

In vitro anticancer studies for the synthesized cyanopyridones revealed that compounds **CP2**, **CP5** and **CP8** induced the greatest effect on EAC cells and they exhibit good anticancer action as per Table 1.

In vitro antioxidant studies explain that compound **CP4** showed significant radical scavenging activity in both methods when compared with the standard drug ascorbic acid. Radical scavenging activity in DPPH and nitric oxide methods increases with concentration and % inhibi-

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme of synthesis of cyanopyridones.

tion at highest concentration 200 µg is shown in the Table 2.

Table 1. Cytotoxicity activities of cyanopyridones by Trypan Blue Exclusion Method

Compd.	R	No. of dead cells (%) at different concentrations (µg/ml)			
		20	50	100	200
Control	1	20	50	100	200
CP1	4-Br	15	20	45	64
CP2	4-NO ₂	21	41	58	80
CP3	4-Cl	12	24	48	68
CP4	4-F	16	29	42	66
CP5	4-NH ₂	20	39	55	78
CP6	4-OH	11	20	41	65
CP7	4-OCH ₃	14	34	42	73
CP8	3-Br	22	40	55	79
Standard	5-Fluorouracil	35	50	90	98

Table 2. Antioxidant activity of cyanopyridones (CP1-CP8)

Compd.	R	DPPH	Nitric oxide
		Radical scavenging activity	free radical scavenging method
		(% inhibition at 200 µg/ml)	
CP1	4-Br	67	79
CP2	4-NO ₂	68	65
CP3	4-Cl	89	78
CP4	4-F	91	81
CP5	4-NH ₂	76	84
CP6	4-OH	85	74
CP7	4-OCH ₃	69	75
CP8	3-Br	90	74
Standard	Ascorbic acid	90	90

Conclusion

The microwave assisted synthesis of novel cyanopyridones has been performed. These compounds were obtained in good yields and confirmed by IR, NMR, Mass and elemental spectral analysis. Biological activity studies showed that compounds exhibited significant anti-tumor and antioxidant activities.

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